

Retrograde Nailing for Distal Third Femur Fractures: A Prospective Study**Dharunraj Venkatasubbu¹, Natarajan², Prince Solomon³, Irfan Sherif⁴, Kalaivanan G⁵, Hari Narayanan⁶**¹Assistant Professor, Department of Orthopaedics, Pondicherry Institute of Medical Sciences, Puducherry, India²Senior Consultant, Department of Orthopaedics, Subha Anandham Medical Centre, Cuddalore, Tamil Nadu, India³Professor, Department of Orthopaedics, Pondicherry Institute of Medical Sciences, Puducherry, India⁴Assistant Professor, Department of Orthopaedics, Pondicherry Institute of Medical Sciences, Puducherry, India⁵Junior Resident, Department of Orthopaedics, Pondicherry Institute of Medical Sciences, Puducherry, India⁶Junior Resident, Department of Orthopaedics, Pondicherry Institute of Medical Sciences, Puducherry, India

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Abstract:**Objectives:** To evaluate the postoperative knee function and results of retrograde nailing for distal third femoral shaft fractures.**Methods:** Between January 2015 and December 2023, a consecutive series of 87 patients (with 94 fractures) who underwent retrograde nailing were prospectively evaluated. Outcome measures were union time, initiation of weight bearing, deformity and shortening, functional length of the nail, knee function assessed using a modified Knee Society Knee Score. Correlations between union time and other variables were also studied.**Results:** In these patients, 88 (93%) of the 94 fractures achieved union, of which 12 underwent dynamization; the mean union time for the other 76 fractures was 4.4 months. Angular malalignment was present in 10 patients and shortening in 9 others. There was negligible correlation between union time and variables of nail-canal diameter mismatch, functional length of nail, fracture geometry, or initiation of partial weight bearing ambulation. Knee flexion of more than 100 degrees was achieved in 81 patients. 29 patients had anterior knee pain and 10 had instability. By the end of one year, excellent or good scores for pain and function were recorded in 87% and 73% respectively, of the 88 patients.**Conclusion:** In view of such favourable union rates but significant deterioration in overall knee joint function, at best retrograde nailing is a reliable alternative in the management of selected complicated fractures of the distal femoral shaft.**Keywords:** Femoral fractures, Fracture fixation, Intramedullary, Retrograde nailing.This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.**Introduction**

The introduction of the interlocking intramedullary nail significantly transformed the management of femoral diaphysis fractures, with the antegrade insertion method becoming the gold standard.[1] Despite its effectiveness, certain limitations of the antegrade technique have led to the development and increasing use of retrograde nailing (RN) for treating femoral shaft fractures.[2] Over the past two decades, RN has gained considerable popularity, particularly in North America. However, two primary concerns have emerged with RN: potential interference with knee function and prolonged healing times for fractures in the distal third of the femoral shaft, a challenge corroborated

by our clinical observations.[3] Despite these concerns, there is a notable lack of comprehensive reports addressing the specific issue of distal femoral shaft fractures managed with RN, as well as detailed evaluations of postoperative knee function.[4,5] Therefore, our study aims to thoroughly assess the postoperative knee function and outcomes associated with retrograde intramedullary nailing in patients with distal third femoral shaft fractures.

Materials and Methods

From January 2015 to December 2023, a consecutive series of patients with fractures in the

distal third of the femoral shaft who underwent retrograde nailing (RN) using the TRIGEN META-NAIL (Smith and Nephew) were prospectively evaluated. The femoral shaft was divided into three equal segments, and only fractures with the primary fracture line in the distal third were included in the study. Exclusion criteria included fractures not involving the lower third of the femoral shaft, grade-III open fractures, and those with an open physeal plate. All relevant data were systematically collected using a standardized proforma.

The outcome measures assessed were the time to union, defined as the period until the patient could walk painlessly without aid and when radiographic evidence showed bridging callus on at least three cortices, and the time to initiation of weight bearing. Additionally, angular deformity was evaluated on anteroposterior and lateral radiographs post-union, while rotational deformity and limb length discrepancy were assessed through clinical examination. The functional length of the nail in each fracture segment, nail-canal diameter mismatch, and knee status according to the Knee Society Score were also evaluated. Malunion was defined as the presence of more than 5° of angular deformity, more than 1 cm of limb length discrepancy, or more than 10° of rotational deformity.

Statistical analyses included Pearson's correlation to study the relationship between the time to union and variables such as nail-canal diameter mismatch and the initiation of partial weight-bearing ambulation. The Chi-squared test was utilized to examine the association between the median time to union and variables including fracture level (lower and middle third junction fractures versus lower third fractures), fracture stability (stable [Winquist-Hansen (WH) types 0, 1, 2] versus unstable), and the number of interlocking screws used. Additionally, the Chi-squared test was applied to study the association between the number of interlocking screws used and the occurrence of malunion.

Results

The present study included 68 male and 26 female patients, totalling 94 fractures, with ages ranging from 20 to 75 years (mean age, 41 years), who met the inclusion criteria. Among these fractures, 51 were on the right side, 43 on the left side, and 7 were bilateral. The injury mechanisms included motor vehicle accidents (n=68), falls from a height (n=24), and incidents while walking or running (n=2). Six patients sustained associated polytrauma to the chest, head, or pelvis, with Injury Severity Scores ranging from 13 to 27 (mean, 19.8). Four of these patients had additional fractures requiring surgical stabilization: one had an ipsilateral tibial fracture; one had ipsilateral tibial and patellar

fractures along with contralateral acetabular and upper femoral shaft fractures; one had associated patellar fractures; and one had an upper limb fracture. For the remaining two patients, one had an ipsilateral tibial fracture, and the other had a patellar fracture. All these patients underwent either simultaneous or sequential stabilization of their associated injuries.

Of the 94 fractures, 46 were located in the distal third of the femoral shaft, and 48 were at the junction of the distal and middle third. There were 20 open fractures (Gustilo grades I & II), and the rest were closed injuries. Comminution was graded according to the Winquist-Hansen classification system. Over a mean follow-up period of 1.5 years, 88 (93%) of the 94 fractures achieved union. Eighty-two fractures united following the initial procedure, while 12 others required dynamization of the implant.

The mean time to union in the first group was 4.4 months (standard deviation [SD], 1.0 month). Twelve patients, showing no evidence of union at three months, underwent dynamization (removal of the proximal screws). Five of these patients achieved union over a mean time of 6.6 months (SD, 2.5 months). One patient with a non-union, whose fracture failed to unite despite dynamization, refused further surgery and continued to ambulate with the aid of a crutch. Another patient was lost to follow-up after six months and was considered a treatment failure. The mean setup time for the RN procedure was 18 minutes (SD, 3 minutes). The mean operation time for patients undergoing RN as an isolated procedure was 88 minutes (SD, 16 minutes).

Based on the stability of the fracture and technical difficulty during locking, all implants were statically locked with either two screws distally (n=13) or one or two screws proximally (n=15). Of the 94 knees evaluated, 81 achieved a flexion of greater than 100°, while one patient (with an associated patellar fracture) achieved only 90° of flexion. The most common complaint was mild anterior knee pain (not interfering with routine activities), recorded in 29 patients. Significant sagittal and coronal plane instability was noted in 10 knees. The overall status of the knee was assessed using the modified Knee Society Knee Score. At postoperative month six, 63% of patients had an excellent or good pain score, while only 37% had excellent or good functional scores. By the end of one year, excellent or good pain and functional scores were recorded in 87% and 73% of patients, respectively. Radiological angular malalignment (>5°) was present in 10 patients, with eight exhibiting valgus malunion and one having anterior angulation at the distal fracture.

However, none were considered to warrant a secondary procedure. Significant limb length discrepancy (>1 cm) was noted in nine patients (mean, 2.25 cm). Four patients reported pain around the distal interlocking screw, managed with analgesics or single screw removal (n=1). Superficial wound infections were evident in four patients (three had a traumatic arthrotomy), which resolved after antibiotic treatment and antiseptic dressings. Of the two patients who had sciatic nerve palsies at the time of injury, one (associated with a segmental fracture) made a partial recovery, while the other did not. No patient experienced

deep infection, fat embolism, heterotopic ossification, or implant failure. Pearson's correlation test showed a negligible correlation between union time and nail-canal diameter mismatch or time to initiation of partial weight bearing. The Chi-squared test (with Yates correction) revealed a statistically significant association between the fracture level and the median time to union, with fractures at the junction of the lower and middle third uniting significantly earlier than those in the lower third. There was no significant association between union time and other parameters.

Preoperative

Postoperative

At 1-year follow up

Figure 1: Non-union with Implant failure treated with retrograde intramedullary nail

Preoperative

Post-operative

Figure 2: Comminuted intraarticular distal femur fracture treated with closed retrograde nail

Discussion

The gold standard treatment in the management of femoral shaft fractures has been closed antegrade intramedullary nailing, with large studies reporting

union rates of more than 97%. [6,7] In patients with polytrauma, RN is an alternative to antegrade nailing for the treatment of femoral shaft fractures, because it is technically easier, allows easier access

to other fractures and obviates the need for traction on a fracture table.

Several authors have advocated the technique to treat bilateral femoral shaft fractures [3, 8, 9] and floating knee injuries, [10,11] since it also enables ipsilateral femoral neck and shaft fractures to be stabilised. [12,13] others have expanded its use to patients with ipsilateral pelvic or acetabular fractures. [14,15] the advantages of intramedullary nailing are that it spares the abductor muscles, thus avoiding incisions in the region of future acetabular surgical approaches and the need for traction on a fracture table (which may stress an unstable pelvis). Obese patients and those with skin lesions in the region of greater trochanter are also suitable for RN. [3,8,12] Patients with femoral head injuries may also benefit, the antegrade approach can lead to significant heterotopic ossification of the hip joint [16,17] and importantly RN shortens the corresponding operation time. [18,19] Over the past 2 decades, RN of the femur has evolved to address some of these limitations of antegrade nailing. For femoral shaft fractures, it achieves union rates varying from 88 to 98%, [20, 21] which are comparable to those of antegrade nailing. Fractures of the distal third of the femoral shaft remain a surgical challenge. Because of its expanding trumpet shape, when stressed the nail may move within the bone. This leads to a loss of reduction on weight bearing, even though the fracture has been well reduced with an antegrade or supracondylar nail. RN provides more stable fixation because of its longer functional length in the fracture fragments and better purchase/adherence at both ends. The present study addresses the particular problem of distal third femoral shaft fractures managed with an RN. We achieved a union rate of 93%, which is comparable to other studies with antegrade nailing as well as RN.[17] In the present study, the mean union time of 4.4 months is more than that for antegrade nailing performed in our institution. Comparative studies [3,20] have revealed that fractures treated by RN take longer to unite, particularly when an unreamed nail is used.

However, others found no difference in the union time between reamed antegrade nailing and RN, which depended on multiple variables (mechanical factors, fracture morphology, and most important of all reaming of the medullary canal).[19] Ostrum et al.[3] Observed that the longer time required for union in retrogradely nailed femurs may be related more to fracture morphology and the surrounding soft tissue injury than to the insertion technique. They localised this problem to fractures at the junction of the middle and distal third, noting that though there were no large nail-canal diameter mismatches at this level, these sites tended to resorb and take longer to unite. Although we expected a correlation between nail-canal diameter

mismatch and the time to union, statistical analysis revealed no relationship. Contrary to Ostrum et al, [3] in our series fractures at the junction of the lower and middle third united significantly earlier than those of the distal third. Moed and Watson [9] also observed that the time to union was also long (15 weeks) in their patients and suggested that static locking might be delaying union. Like us, many others have observed the increased need for dynamization of the implant to achieve union by RN, [9,17] and 19% of our cases needed dynamization to achieve fracture union. The most common technical difficulty encountered during the RN procedure was free hand proximal locking. As the implant used was the standard antegrade femoral nail, the proximal locking was in the lateral-to medial direction. Although this eliminated the risk of neurovascular injury during placement of the interlocking screw, visualisation of its hole was difficult. In addition, the bulk of soft tissue in the proximal thigh increases the risk of the screw getting lost. [15,16] suggested remedial measures include: the use of a sandbag under the ipsilateral hip, making a generous incision, and tying an absorbable suture around the screw. Due to these technical difficulties, in a few patients we restricted proximal locking to a single screw. The number of screws used did not have any correlation with fracture union time or alignment. We also observed that when the nail length fell short of the lesser trochanter, the locking process became easier. Whether this compromises the stability of the fixation or increases stress at the subtrochanteric region needs further study. Knee pain, knee stiffness, quadriceps atrophy, articular cartilage damage, and synovial metallosis are the potential problems of the RN procedure, which prevent its wide acceptance. Although knee stiffness following RN has been a major concern, several studies have shown that the range of movement is not adversely affected. [3] In our series, 93% (26) of the operated knees achieved $>100^\circ$ of flexion (mean, 123°). The only patient whose range of knee flexion was more limited, had an associated ipsilateral patellar fracture.

Comparative studies [3,19] have shown no difference in the incidence of knee pain between antegrade nailing and RN. Anterior knee pain has multiple causes (e.g. cartilage injury from initial trauma or quadriceps atrophy) and may not be due to the retrograde nail per se. [3] In our study, it was the most common complaint (70%), noted even as late as one year postoperatively. In most patients it was not so severe as to interfere with activities of daily living, and only 3 (11%) required medication for pain relief. 53% of the patients with anterior knee pain had ligamentous instability of the knee, but there was no record of preoperative assessment for comparison. As RN does not interfere with the anterior cruciate or collateral ligaments, the likely

cause of such instability is the initial trauma itself. Indeed, the incidence of ligamentous injury following fractures of the femoral shaft range from 5 to 48%, but to what extent this ligamentous instability contributes to knee pain is unknown. Postoperative function of the knee has always been evaluated in terms of knee pain and/or range of movement, rather than as a comprehensive function. Though the Knee Society Knee Score was developed in relation to total knee replacement surgery, [22] the first 2 components of the scoring system (knee score and knee function score) provided a suitable instrument for overall assessment in our study; the categorical score was omitted as it was not relevant. RN appeared to have a detrimental effect on the knee, as seen by the reduced knee score even one year postoperatively. The high incidence of knee instability compromises the knee score, though as mentioned already its aetiology is probably unrelated to the nailing.[23] Hence, to attribute the low overall knee scores entirely to the RN procedure may be inappropriate. Irrespective of aetiology, the fact remains that the knee function is compromised in at least 27% of the patients, which is contrary to the claims of many authors reporting that knee function is not significantly compromised. This contradiction could also be related to different parameters used to assess the knee joint, variations in surgical technique or the joint mobilisation protocol. The status of the operated knees improved over time; the mean pain score improved from 70 (SD, 16) at 6 months to 82 (SD, 16.) at one year and the mean functional score from 60 (SD, 21) to 80 (SD, 22). However, further studies with longer follow-up should give a clearer picture. Other complications associated with RN of the femur include malalignment, knee joint sepsis, neurovascular injury during proximal screw placement, symptomatic distal interlocking screws, and heterotopic ossification.[24] The reported incidence of malunion varies from 2.2 to 42%, which is probably due to variations in the definition of malunion. Using the criteria mentioned earlier, 4 of our patients had angular malunion and 4 had limb length discrepancy; none of them received additional surgical procedures to correct these deformities. The reported incidence of symptomatic distal interlocking screws varies from 9% to 33%. Our 4 patients were managed either with analgesics or single screw removal (n=1). There is a potential risk for injury to the femoral artery and nerve during placement of the proximal anterior to-posterior interlocking screw.[25,26] However, as the direction of its placement was lateral-to-medial in our series, we did not encounter this problem. Nor did our patients develop, knee sepsis or heterotopic ossification around the joint, both of which are recognised risks.

Conclusion

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Though the results of RN for distal third femoral shaft fractures are encouraging in terms of union, we recommend its use with caution, due to significant deterioration in overall knee joint function. There is no significant correlation between the time taken for union and variables such as the type of fracture, nail-canal diameter mismatch, and functional length of the nail in each fracture segment. More detailed studies with longer follow-up are required before accepting RN as routine. Nonetheless, RN is a reliable alternative in the management of selected complicated fractures of the distal femoral shaft.

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